

- 1 An internal validity item bank including items of relevance for *in vitro* studies
- 2 [Supplementary Materials 2](#)
- 3 [Focus group participant characteristics](#)

Country of residence	Belgium; Canada; Germany; Italy; Netherlands; Norway; Sweden; United States of America
Main employer	Center for Alternatives to Animal Testing - Europe European Commission Joint Research Centre Freelance medical writer and consultant German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment Institute for In Vitro Sciences Institute of Marine Research Konstanz University Karolinska Institutet Leibniz Research Institute for Environmental Medicine National Institute of Occupational Health Norwegian Institute of Public Health Procter & Gamble Services NV National Institute for Health and the Environment Self-employed TEAM mastery S.r.l. The Climate and Environmental Research Institute United States Environmental Protection Agency University of California Irvine University of Ottawa
Gender	Female: 15; Male: 5
Years of experience with <i>in vitro</i> studies	No experience: 1* 1-3 years: 0 4-6 years: 2 More than 6 years: 17

Years of experience with chemical risk assessment	No experience: 2 1-3 years: 3 4-6 years: 0 More than 6 years: 15
Years of experience with systematic reviews	No experience: 5 Some experience (<i>e.g. been involved in one systematic review or peer-reviewed several systematic reviews</i>): 8 Moderate experience (<i>conducted study appraisal in at least one systematic review</i>): 4 Extensive experience (<i>have designed the methods, including selection, modification, or developed study assessment methods, for at least one systematic review</i>): 3

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5 *One person didn't have hands on experience doing *in vitro* research and reported 0 years of
 6 experience. However, this person is, and have been, involved in much relevant work on *in*
 7 *vitro* studies such as e.g. development of adverse outcome pathways, so we still found that
 8 this person had valuable *in vitro* expertise.

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